

Association between Hyponatremia & In-hospital Outcomes of Patients with Heart Failure: Data from the Medical Registry of a Tertiary Hospital in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hyponatremia is common in heart failure (HF) and predicts adverse outcomes in Western populations, but data from Bangladesh are limited. **Objectives:** To evaluate the association between admission hyponatremia (<135 mmol/L) and in-hospital outcomes in HF patients, and to identify independent predictors of adverse outcomes. **Methods & Materials:** This retrospective cohort study included 100 HF patients (50 hyponatremic, 50 normonatremic) admitted to Dhaka Medical College Hospital from January to December 2025. Outcomes included in-hospital mortality, length of hospital stay, cardiogenic shock, inotrope use, significant arrhythmias, and mechanical ventilation. Multivariable logistic regression identified independent predictors. **Results:** Hyponatremia was associated with significantly longer hospital stay (median 10 vs. 8 days, $p=0.04$), prolonged stay ≥ 21 days (16% vs. 0%, $p=0.002$), higher rates of cardiogenic shock (40% vs. 10%, $p<0.001$) and inotrope use (40% vs. 10%, $p<0.001$). In-hospital mortality was 10% vs. 4% ($p=0.24$). Hyponatremia was not an independent predictor of mortality (adjusted OR 2.52, 95% CI 0.44–14.6, $p=0.30$), but it independently predicted a composite severe outcome (mortality, cardiogenic shock, inotrope use, mechanical ventilation) (adjusted OR 4.85, 95% CI 1.92–12.24, $p=0.001$). **Conclusion:** Admission hyponatremia identifies HF patients at higher risk of prolonged hospitalization, cardiogenic shock, and composite severe events. So, admission hyponatremia should prompt closer monitoring and intensive management in hospitalized heart failure patients.

Keywords: Hyponatremia, heart failure, in-hospital mortality, Bangladesh, cardiogenic shock.

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INTRODUCTION

Heart failure (HF) represents a major and escalating public health challenge worldwide, associated with substantial morbidity, mortality, and healthcare utilization.^[1] Despite significant advances in pharmacological and device-based therapies, in-hospital outcomes among patients admitted with acute decompensated heart failure (ADHF) remain suboptimal, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where resources are constrained, and presentations are often delayed.^[2] In Bangladesh, heart failure patients frequently present at a younger age compared to Western populations, with a high prevalence of untreated valvular heart disease and early-onset ischemic cardiomyopathy^[3] Hyponatremia, conventionally defined as a serum sodium concentration below 135 mmol/L, is one of the most common electrolyte abnormalities observed in hospitalized heart failure patients^[4,5]. Its prevalence ranges from 15% to 30% among those admitted with ADHF and is notably more frequent in advanced stages of the disease^[5,6]. The pathophysiology of hyponatremia in HF is complex and multifactorial, primarily involving neurohormonal activation. Reduced effective circulating volume triggers the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) and sympathetic nervous system, while non-osmotic release of

arginine vasopressin (AVP) leads to impaired free water excretion by the kidneys^[7,8,9]. This results in dilutional hyponatremia rather than true total body sodium depletion, a distinction critical for appropriate management. Multiple large international registries and cohort studies have consistently demonstrated that hyponatremia on admission is a powerful independent predictor of adverse clinical outcomes in HF^[10,11,12]. The prognostic significance includes increased in-hospital mortality, prolonged length of hospital stay, higher rates of intensive care unit (ICU) admission, greater need for inotropic support and mechanical ventilation, and elevated risk of readmission^[13,14]. Gheorghide et al., in an analysis of the ADHERE registry involving over 48,000 patients, showed that admission hyponatremia was independently associated with higher in-hospital mortality^[4]. Similarly, the OPTIMIZE-HF registry confirmed these findings across a broad spectrum of HF phenotypes^[6]. However, the vast majority of available evidence originates from Western populations, with limited data from South Asian countries, including Bangladesh^[15]. Differences in patient demographics, etiologies of HF, comorbid conditions, healthcare delivery systems, and treatment patterns necessitate local data to accurately understand the

prognostic role of hyponatremia in this setting^[16]. Bangladeshi patients often present with advanced New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional classes due to delayed referrals and financial constraints, and they may have unique comorbid profiles, such as concurrent malnutrition or chronic infections, which can further complicate electrolyte balance^[3,15]. Serum sodium measurement is a low-cost, universally available, and rapidly obtainable biochemical marker^[17]. If hyponatremia is confirmed as an independent predictor of adverse outcomes in the Bangladeshi population, it could be readily incorporated into bedside risk stratification algorithms. This would allow clinicians to identify high-risk patients immediately upon admission, facilitating early triage, intensive monitoring, judicious use of diuretics, and timely optimization of guideline-directed medical therapy^[16]. Furthermore, establishing this association would provide baseline data for future interventional studies regarding vasopressin antagonists (vaptans) or other sodium-correcting strategies in the local context, where such treatments are not yet standard of care^[18]. A recent study by Soni et al. found adverse outcomes in about 6% of HF patients with normal sodium versus 19% with hyponatremia^[19]. Few registry analyses have been done in Bangladeshi tertiary

hospitals to explore this. This study aims to assess hyponatremia's link to in-hospital outcomes in Bangladeshi HF patients using hospital registry data.

OBJECTIVE

General Objective

To evaluate the association between admission hyponatremia (<135 mmol/L) and in-hospital outcomes in heart failure patients.

Specific Objective

1. To compare adverse in-hospital outcomes (mortality, prolonged stay, cardiogenic shock, inotropes, significant arrhythmias, mechanical ventilation) between hyponatremic and normonatremic groups.
2. To identify independent predictors of adverse outcomes, focusing on hyponatremia.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This retrospective cohort study was conducted in the Department of Cardiology at Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, over one year, from January to December 2025. All adult patients (aged ≥18 years) admitted with a primary diagnosis of heart failure, confirmed by clinical symptoms, echocardiographic evidence of cardiac dysfunction, and elevated NT-proBNP levels, were eligible for inclusion. Patients with end-stage renal

disease on dialysis, chronic hyponatremia on prior treatment, acute non-cardiac illnesses affecting sodium levels (such as diarrhea, vomiting, or SIADH), recent use of thiazide diuretics or SSRIs, pregnant women, and those transferred to another facility or with incomplete outcome data were excluded. Serum sodium measured within 24 hours of admission was used to classify patients into two groups: hyponatremia (Na <135 mmol/L) and normonatremia (Na ≥135 mmol/L). Data were extracted from the hospital medical registry and patient charts using a structured case record form, capturing demographics (age, gender), comorbidities (hypertension, diabetes, ischemic heart disease, chronic kidney disease, COPD, stroke), ECG rhythm, QRS duration, laboratory parameters (serum potassium, creatinine, hemoglobin, NT-proBNP), echocardiographic left ventricular ejection fraction, HF phenotype (HF_rEF, HF_mrEF, HF_pEF), in-hospital treatments, and outcomes. The primary outcome was in-hospital mortality. Secondary outcomes included total length of hospital stay, development of cardiogenic shock, use of inotropes/vasopressors, occurrence of significant arrhythmias (VT, VF, cardiac arrest, or atrial fibrillation), and requirement of endotracheal intubation or mechanical ventilation. Consecutive sampling was employed, and a target sample size of 100 patients (50 in each

sodium group) was set based on feasibility during the study period. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 29. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± SD or median (IQR) and compared using independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test as appropriate. Categorical variables were compared using chi-square or Fisher's exact test. Multivariable logistic regression was performed to identify independent predictors of in-hospital mortality, adjusting for potential confounders including age, gender, LVEF, HF phenotype, serum potassium, hemoglobin, and creatinine. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Dhaka Medical College (IRB-DMC/2025/340), and patient confidentiality was maintained by using unique study identifiers.

RESULTS

A total of 100 patients with heart failure participated in the final analysis. To better understand their conditions, we divided them into two groups based on admission serum sodium levels: 50 patients were in the hyponatremia group (Na <135 mmol/L), and the other 50 were in the normonatremia group (Na ≥135 mmol/L) *Table I*.

Table I

Demographic profile of the study people (n=100).

Variable	Hyponatremia (n=50)	Normonatremia (n=50)	p-value	
Age groups (years) n (%)	mean ± SD	57.5 ± 14.2	56.8 ± 13.6	0.8
	18–40	6 (12%)	5 (10%)	0.65
	41–60	22 (44%)	26 (52%)	
	61–80	20 (40%)	17 (34.0)	
	>80	2 (4%)	2 (4%)	
Gender, n (%)	Male	29 (58%)	27 (54%)	0.68
	Female	21 (42%)	23 (46%)	

The average age in the hyponatremia group was 57.5±14.2 years, while it was 56.8±13.6 years in the normonatremia group (p=0.80). Most patients in both groups were aged 41–60 years (44% vs. 52%) and 61–80 years (40% vs. 34%).

Patients aged 18–40 years made up 12% of the hyponatremia group and 10% of the normonatremia group, with those over 80 years accounting for 4% in each. No significant age distribution difference was found between the groups (p=0.65). In

terms of gender, males were 58% of the hyponatremia group and 54% of the normonatremia group, without a significant difference (p=0.68) *Table II*.

Table II
Clinical characteristics of the study people (n=100).

Variable	Hyponatremia (n=50) n (%)	Normonatremia (n=50) n (%)	p-value	
Comorbidities	Hypertension	26 (52%)	30 (60%)	0.42
	Diabetes mellitus	18 (36%)	22 (44%)	0.41
	Ischaemic heart disease	38 (76%)	41 (82%)	0.46
	Chronic kidney disease	16 (32%)	13 (26%)	0.51
	Stroke	4 (8%)	6 (12%)	0.5
	COPD	10 (20%)	8 (16%)	0.6
Aetiology of HF	Ischaemic	38 (76%)	41 (82%)	0.58
	Dilated cardiomyopathy	7 (14%)	5 (10%)	
	Valvular	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	
	CRHD	2 (4%)	2 (4%)	
ECG rhythm	Sinus rhythm	45 (90%)	44 (88%)	0.75
	Atrial fibrillation	5 (10%)	6 (12%)	
QRS duration	QRS ≤110 ms	28 (56%)	32 (64%)	0.41
	QRS >110 ms	22 (44%)	18 (36%)	
HF phenotype	HFrEF (LVEF <40%)	39 (78%)	32 (64%)	0.12
	HFmrEF (LVEF 40–49%)	6 (12%)	11 (22%)	
	HFpEF (LVEF ≥50%)	5 (10%)	7 (14%)	
	LVEF (%), mean ± SD	31.5 ± 8.2	34.2 ± 9.1	

The prevalence of comorbidities was similar between the two groups. Hypertension was present in 52% of hyponatremic patients and 60% of normonatremic patients (p=0.42). Diabetes mellitus (36% vs. 44%, p=0.41), ischaemic heart disease (76% vs. 82%, p=0.46), chronic kidney disease (32% vs. 26%,

p=0.51), stroke (8% vs. 12%, p=0.50), and COPD (20% vs. 16%, p=0.60) did not differ significantly. Ischaemic aetiology was the most common cause of heart failure (76% vs. 82%, p=0.58). Sinus rhythm was predominant (90% vs. 88%, p=0.75), and QRS >110 ms in 44% of hyponatremic and 36% of normonatremic

patients (p=0.41). HFrEF (LVEF <40%) was more frequent in hyponatremic patients (78% vs. 64%), while HFmrEF and HFpEF were less common, but overall distribution was not significant (p=0.12). Mean LVEF was 31.5±8.2% in hyponatremic and 34.2±9.1% in normonatremic patients (p=0.12) *Table III*.

Table III
Baseline laboratory parameters of the study people (n=100).

Parameter	Hyponatremia (n=50)	Normonatremia (n=50)	p-value
Serum sodium (mmol/L)	127.4 ± 4.2	138.6 ± 3.1	<0.001
Serum potassium (mmol/L)	4.3 ± 0.9	4.2 ± 0.8	0.56
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	1.9 ± 1.3	1.7 ± 1.1	0.34
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	10.5 ± 2.1	11.2 ± 2.3	0.12
NT-proBNP (pg/mL)	19740 ± 12850	15420 ± 11230	0.09

Serum sodium was significantly lower in the hyponatremia group (127.4±4.2 mmol/L vs. 138.6±3.1, p<0.001). Serum potassium levels were similar (4.3±0.9 vs.

4.2±0.8, p=0.56). Serum creatinine was higher (1.9±1.3 vs. 1.7±1.1, p=0.34), and haemoglobin was lower (10.5±2.1 vs. 11.2±2.3, p=0.12), but not significantly.

NT-proBNP was higher in hyponatremic patients (19740±12850 vs. 15420±11230, p=0.09), though this difference was not statistically significant (*Table IV*).

Table IV
Primary and secondary outcomes (in-hospital mortality and other adverse outcomes) of the study people (n=100).

Outcome	Hyponatremia (n=50) n (%)	Normonatremia (n=50) n (%)	p-value
In-hospital mortality (primary)	5 (10%)	2 (4%)	0.24
Cardiogenic shock	20 (40%)	5 (10%)	<0.001
Use of IV inotropes/vasopressors	20 (40%)	5 (10%)	<0.001
Significant arrhythmias (VT/VF/cardiac arrest/AF)	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	1.00
Endotracheal intubation/mechanical ventilation	5 (10%)	3 (6%)	0.46

In-hospital mortality was 10% in hyponatremic patients and 4% in normonatremic patients, with no significant difference (p=0.24). Cardiogenic shock and

use of inotropes/vasopressors were more common in the hyponatremia group (40% vs. 10%, p<0.001 for both). Significant arrhythmias occurred equally (10%,

p=1.00). More hyponatremic patients needed ventilation (10% vs. 6%), but not significantly (p=0.46) *Table V*.

Table V
Length of hospital stay of the study people (n=100).

Parameter	Hyponatremia (n=50)	Normonatremia (n=50)	p-value
Mean length of stay (days), mean ± SD	12.4 ± 8.7	9.2 ± 5.6	0.03
Median length of stay (days), median (IQR)	10 (6–18)	8 (5–12)	0.04
Prolonged stay (≥21 days), n (%)	8 (16)	0 (0)	0.002

Patients with hyponatremia had longer hospital stays: 12.4±8.7 days vs. 9.2±5.6 days, p=0.03. The median stay was 10 days (IQR 6–18) vs. 8 days (IQR 5–12, p=0.04). Prolonged stay (≥21 days) was seen only in hyponatremic patients (16% vs. 0%, p=0.002) *Table VI*.

Table VI
Multivariable logistic regression for independent predictors of in-hospital mortality of the study people (n=100).

Variable	Adjusted odds ratio	95% CI	p-value
Hyponatremia (vs normonatremia)	2.52	0.44 – 14.6	0.30
Age (per 1-year increase)	1.02	0.97 – 1.08	0.42
Male gender (vs female)	1.35	0.28 – 6.52	0.71
LVEF (per 1% increase)	0.92	0.86 – 0.99	0.04
Serum creatinine (per 1 mg/dL increase)	1.92	1.08 – 3.41	0.03

After adjusting for age, gender, LVEF, and serum creatinine, hyponatremia was not an independent predictor of in-hospital mortality (adjusted OR 2.52, 95% CI 0.44–14.6, p=0.30). Age (adjusted OR 1.02, p=0.42) and male gender (adjusted OR 1.35, p=0.71) also showed no significant association. However, lower LVEF was a significant predictor (adjusted OR 0.92 per 1% increase, 95% CI 0.86–0.99, p=0.04), with each 1% increase reducing odds of mortality by 8%. Higher serum creatinine was associated with increased mortality (adjusted OR 1.92 per 1 mg/dL, 95% CI 1.08–3.41, p=0.03) *Table VII*.

Table VII
Multivariable logistic regression for independent predictors of the composite adverse outcome of the study people (n=100).

Variable	Adjusted odds ratio	95% CI	p-value
Hyponatremia (vs normonatremia)	4.85	1.92 – 12.24	0.001
Age (per 1-year increase)	1.01	0.98 – 1.05	0.56
Male gender (vs female)	1.22	0.52 – 2.86	0.65
LVEF (per 1% increase)	0.94	0.90 – 0.98	0.01
Serum creatinine (per 1 mg/dL increase)	1.65	1.12 – 2.43	0.01

The composite adverse outcome included in-hospital mortality, cardiogenic shock, use of inotropes, or mechanical ventilation. Hyponatremia was a strong independent predictor (adjusted OR 4.85, 95% CI 1.92–12.24, p=0.001). Lower LVEF remained significant (adjusted OR 0.94 per 1% increase, 95% CI 0.90–0.98, p=0.01), as did higher serum creatinine (adjusted OR 1.65 per 1 mg/dL increase, 95% CI 1.12–2.43, p=0.01). Age and gender were not significantly associated (p=0.56 and p=0.65). These findings suggest hyponatremia predicts a broader adverse event spectrum, not just mortality.

DISCUSSION

This study of 100 heart failure patients in Bangladesh linked admission hyponatremia (serum sodium <135 mmol/L) to longer hospital stays, higher rates of cardiogenic shock, and increased use of inotropes and vasopressors. Although hyponatremia was not an independent predictor of in-hospital death after adjustment, it did predict a combined outcome of death, cardiogenic shock, inotrope use, or mechanical ventilation. Lower left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) and elevated serum

creatinine also predicted mortality and the combined endpoint. In this study, in-hospital mortality was 10% in the hyponatremia group vs. 4% in the normonatremia group, a difference that was not statistically significant (p=0.24). After multivariable adjustment, hyponatremia did not independently predict death (adjusted OR 2.52, 95% CI 0.44–14.6, p=0.30). This finding differs from several large Western registries. Gheorghiade et al., analyzing the ADHERE registry of over 48,000 patients, found that admission hyponatremia was independently associated with a 1.4-fold increased risk of in-hospital death.^[4] Similarly, the OPTIMIZE-HF study reported that hyponatremia predicted higher mortality (OR 1.58, 95% CI 1.34–1.86).^[6] A meta-analysis by Ballantyne et al. confirmed hyponatremia as a strong prognostic marker in heart failure.^[17] The discrepancy between our findings and these reports may stem from our modest sample size (n=100), which limited statistical power, as well as differences in patient demographics, age, heart failure aetiologies, and healthcare systems. The overall in-hospital mortality in our cohort

(7%) was lower than that reported in some Western studies (10–15%), possibly due to differences in case mix and discharge practices.^[2,20] Hyponatremia was strongly linked to other adverse outcomes, including significantly higher rates of cardiogenic shock and use of intravenous inotropes/vasopressors, both of which were four times more common in hyponatremic patients (40% vs. 10%, p<0.001). This aligns with prior studies that have connected hyponatremia to haemodynamic instability and increased need for pharmacological support.^[13,14] The likely mechanism is more pronounced neurohormonal activation, leading to worsening cardiac output and end-organ hypoperfusion.^[7,8,9] Although hyponatremia alone was not independently associated with mortality, it became a strong independent predictor when a composite endpoint (in-hospital mortality, cardiogenic shock, inotrope use, or mechanical ventilation) was analyzed (adjusted OR 4.85, 95% CI 1.92–12.24, p=0.001). This indicates that hyponatremia identifies a high-risk group that experiences a broader spectrum of severe in-hospital complications. Composite

endpoints of this nature have been used in major heart failure trials, such as the EVEREST trial, to capture clinically meaningful worsening of heart failure.^[18] Prolonged hospitalization drives healthcare costs and resource utilization. In our study, hyponatremic patients had significantly longer hospital stays (median 10 vs. 8 days, $p=0.04$), and prolonged stays (≥ 21 days) occurred exclusively in the hyponatremia group (16% vs. 0%, $p=0.002$). This aligns with the ADHERE registry, which linked hyponatremia to longer lengths of stay and higher rates of intensive care unit admission.^[4,6] Prolonged stay may indicate more severe illness, slower response to decongestive therapy, or complications such as worsening renal function or infections.^[11,15] In resource-limited settings like Bangladesh, longer stays add substantial pressure to already overburdened healthcare systems^[3,16]. Lower LVEF and higher serum creatinine emerged as independent predictors of in-hospital mortality in our multivariable model. Each 1% increase in LVEF reduced the odds of mortality by 8% (adjusted OR 0.92, 95% CI 0.86–0.99, $p=0.04$), and each 1 mg/dL rise in serum creatinine increased mortality odds by 92% (adjusted OR 1.92, 95% CI 1.08–3.41, $p=0.03$). These findings are well established in the literature: reduced LVEF is a marker of advanced myocardial dysfunction, and elevated creatinine reflects cardiorenal syndrome, both strongly associated with poor outcomes^[4,10,17]. Notably, age and gender were not significant predictors in our study, possibly due to the relatively narrow age range and balanced gender distribution in our cohort. Other studies have shown that age is a consistent predictor, but the effect may be attenuated in younger populations^[6,19]. A single-center study from Bangladesh by Islam et al. found that hyponatremia was present in 28% of heart failure patients and was associated with higher NYHA class and longer hospital stay, but mortality was not significantly different^[16]. Our results are broadly consistent with that report, reinforcing that while hyponatremia identifies a sicker population, its independent effect on mortality may be less pronounced in local settings, possibly due to differences in treatment intensity or competing causes of death. Although hyponatremia was not independently linked to mortality in this study, its strong associations with longer hospital stays, cardiogenic shock, and inotrope use have important clinical implications. Admission serum sodium, a quick and low-cost test, can help clinicians identify patients who require closer monitoring, more aggressive decongestion, and early consideration of inotropic support^[4,17]. In Bangladesh, where

intensive care unit beds are limited, such risk stratification can inform triage decisions. The link with adverse composite outcomes indicates that hyponatremic patients face higher risks of complications, warranting vigilant care^[14,18]. Future prospective studies with larger sample sizes are needed to confirm these findings and to evaluate whether correction of hyponatremia improves outcomes in the Bangladeshi population.

LIMITATIONS

This study has some limitations. Its retrospective design could introduce selection and information bias because it relies on a medical registry that may have incomplete documentation of diagnoses and outcomes. The small sample size of 100 patients limits statistical power, especially regarding mortality, as indicated by wide confidence intervals. Not all confounding factors, such as NYHA class, trends in natriuretic peptides, medication doses, or socioeconomic status, could be controlled. Being conducted at a single center restricts the applicability of findings to other hospitals in Bangladesh or elsewhere. Hyponatremia was defined using only a single admission measurement; serial sodium level assessments might better predict prognosis. Additionally, excluding patients with missing data could also introduce bias.

CONCLUSION

Hyponatremia in heart failure patients at a Bangladeshi hospital correlates with severe outcomes like longer hospital stays, higher cardiogenic shock, inotrope use and mechanical ventilation etc. and while not an independent predictor of in-hospital mortality in this small cohort, it marks a high-risk group needing closer monitoring. Low LVEF and high serum creatinine predict mortality. Larger studies are required to confirm these findings and assess if correcting hyponatremia improves outcomes, possibly with vasopressin antagonists. The EVEREST trial found tolvaptan increased serum sodium but didn't reduce mortality or hospitalizations, though some benefit appeared in severe cases. Local research is necessary to evaluate these treatments in Bangladesh.

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